

number of available H^+ ions competing with the metal ions in the exchange process.

The utility of cerium(IV) antimonate papers in electrochromatography is demonstrated by achieving several important and analytically difficult ternary and binary separations. On the basis of qualitative separation achieved, the quantitative separation of Pd^{2+} from several metal ions in simple aqueous electrolytes like 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M HCl+0.1 M NH_4Cl (1 : 1) is possible in only 3 h under a potential of 150 V. Apart from binary separations, Pd^{2+} (2–10 μg) was also quantitatively separated from different synthetic mixtures. In all, five synthetic mixtures were prepared by taking 5 μg each of the following cations: Bi^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Au^{3+} , Se^{4+} and Mo^{6+} along with Pd^{2+} . The amount of Pd^{2+} varied from 2–10 μg in these synthetic samples.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistances from U.G.C., New Delhi to one of the authors (S.A.) and from C.S.T. (U.P.) to the other (A.K.M.) are gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. M. QURESHI, K. G. VARSHNEY and R. P. S. RAJPUT, *Ann. Chem.*, 1976, 66, 337.
2. R. P. S. RAJPUT and N. S. SETH, *Chromatographia*, 1980, 13, 219.
3. N. S. SETH and R. P. S. RAJPUT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 1088.
4. J. S. GILL and S. N. TANDON, *Talanta*, 1972, 19, 1355.
5. F. FEIGEL, "Spot Tests in Inorganic Analysis", 5th. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1958.
6. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 716.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Disodium Ethylene-1,2-bisdithiocarbamate by Extraction of its Molybdenum Complex into Isobutyl Methyl Ketone

A. L. J. RAO*

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002
and

NEELAM VERMA

Department of Chemistry, T.I.E.T., Patiala-147 001

Manuscript received 18 March 1988, accepted 18 July 1988

DITHIOCARBAMATE have many uses, they are widely used as pesticides, especially as their metal complexes, and are applied in the rubber industry as vulcanisation accelerators and anti-oxidants. Most of the analytical methods in general use, are based on the Clarke method¹.

Dithiocarbamate pesticide residues, however, have been analysed²⁻⁴ by determining the released carbon disulphide spectrophotometrically, but these are time-consuming processes. It is considered of interest to determine dithiocarbamate (nabam) by a simple, direct and rapid spectrophotometric method.

We present here a more sensitive and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of nabam after extracting its molybdenum complex into isobutyl methyl ketone.

Experimental

A Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer was used for recording absorption measurements. Nabam was crystallised from a solution (Wilson Laboratories, Bombay). Ether was added to precipitate the dithiocarbamate, which was filtered off, recrystallised twice by dissolving in ethanol and precipitating with ether; the product was a hexahydrate. Purity was checked by elemental analysis and m.p (82°) and found to be the same as given in the literature. A 0.1% solution of nabam was prepared in distilled water and standardised¹ and further diluted as desired with distilled water. A 2% (w/v) sodium molybdate solution was prepared in distilled water. Stock solutions of other elements were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water. Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing solutions of the elements to give the required composition.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 500 μg nabam in a beaker was added 2M H_2SO_4 (1.5–2.0 ml) and 2% sodium molybdate solution (2.0 ml). The final volume was made to 5 ml with distilled water. The solution was boiled for 5–7 min, then cooled and the final volume was again made to 5 ml with distilled water. The aqueous solution was transferred to a separatory funnel and shaken with isobutyl methyl ketone (5 ml) for 1 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the organic phase was transferred into a dry tube containing anhydrous calcium chloride. Extract with another 5 ml of methyl isobutyl ketone from the aqueous phase gave negligible absorbance indicating extraction of the complex in the first step itself. The absorbance of the dried solution (first step) was taken and measured at 670 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of nabam–Mo complex in MIBK was recorded against the reagent blank. The complex absorbed strongly at 670 nm. The absorbance of the extract increased with the addition of upto 1.5–2.0 ml of 2 M H_2SO_4 but decreased with further addition. The absorbance of the extract remained constant for 2.0–3.0 ml of 2% sodium molybdate solution and the

absorbance was same when the complex was boiled for 5–7 min. The complex was not extractable into benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, toluene, and hexane but could be extracted with n-butyl acetate, amyl acetate, diethyl ether, butan-2-one, ethyl acetate, acetyl acetate, isobutanol and methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK). Maximum absorbance was observed with MIBK and hence it was used in this method. The absorbance of the complex remained practically constant for 30 min.

Under optimum conditions described above, a calibration curve was constructed at 670 nm, and Beer's law being obeyed in the concentration range 25.0–700 μg per 5 ml of the final solution. The Sandell's sensitivity was calculated to be 1.25 μg cm^{-2} at 670 nm (for an absorbance of 0.001) and aliquot containing 500 μg of nabam gave mean absorption of 0.40 with a relative standard deviation of 0.0025.

Composition of the Mo–nabam complex was studied by Job's method of continuous variation, and was found to be 2 : 1.

Effect of diverse ions: Sample solutions containing 250 μg of nabam and various amounts of different alkali metal salts or metal ions were prepared and the determination of nabam was studied and the general procedure was applied. The following foreign ions (μg , amounts in parentheses) did not interfere in the determination of nabam 250 μg in 5 ml of the final solution: Pb^{2+} (510), Zn^{2+} (66), Bi^{3+} (20), Cd^{2+} (42), Fe^{2+} (10) and Mn^{2+} (10). Cu^{2+} interfered strongly.

Potassium bromide (25 mg), sodium acetate (25 mg), sodium citrate (12 mg), potassium iodide (1 mg), sodium potassium tartrate (10 mg), potassium oxalate (180 μg), ammonium thiocyanate (150 μg) and ethylene diamine (12 mg) were tolerated. EDTA, potassium chloride, potassium nitrate and sodium thiosulphate interfered strongly.

Interference of some of the common reagents like ziram, ferbam, thiram, zineb and maneb which are mostly used as pesticides has been studied. Ziram, ferbam and thiram if present with nabam can be removed by extraction with chloroform. Nabam remaining in the aqueous phase can be determined by the general procedure. Zineb and maneb if present with nabam can be easily separated by extraction with acetonitrile.

Simultaneous determination of nabam and ziram (zinc dimethyl dithiocarbamate) were carried out. Synthetic mixtures of nabam and ziram in various proportions were prepared. Taking advantage of the solubility difference and the colour of the Mo–nabam (blue) and Mo–ziram (yellow), nabam and ziram can be determined simultaneously. Binary mixture was dissolved in 0.1 N NaOH solution. To this solution was added appropriate amount of H_2SO_4 acid and sodium molybdate. Yellow coloured complex formed by ziram with molyb-

denum in cold was extractable into MIBK, whereas blue coloured complex of nabam–Mo was not extractable in cold. Hence, aqueous phase was boiled for 5–7 min, then cooled and extracted with MIBK. The absorbance of the extracts were measured at 420 nm for ziram–Mo complex and at 670 nm for nabam–Mo complex and the amount of ziram and nabam was determined from the respective calibration curves. Similarly, simultaneous determinations of nabam and thiram, and nabam and ferbam were possible.

Applications: The wide applicability of the method was tested by the satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples containing nabam upto 500 μg in the aliquot. The method is quite selective for nabam determination in the presence of zineb, maneb, ziram, thiram and ferbam. The proposed method is quite simple and rapid as it takes less than 15 min for nabam determination after preparation of nabam solution. Binary mixtures of nabam and ziram, nabam and thiram, and nabam and ferbam can be determined simultaneously. It is one of the sensitive methods available for nabam determination and could be used in the analysis of commercial samples.

References

1. D. G. CLARKE, H. BAUM, E. L. STANLEY and W. E. HESTER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 1842.
2. Institute Superiore di Sanita, *Boll. Chim. Umone Ital.*, 1980, 6, 619.
3. Z. CHMIEL, *Chem. Anal.*, 1979, 24, 505.
4. A. T. LONGBOTTOM and E. JAMES, *Govt. Rep. Ann. Index (US)*, 1982, 82, 1544.

Synthetic and Analytical Studies on Pearl 'Bhasma'

RAJESH DIXIT and G. C. SHIVAHARE*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan,
Jaipur-302 004

*Manuscript received 16 November 1987, revised 17 June 1988,
accepted 18 July 1988*

PEARL 'bhasma' is a product used in Indian System of Medicine (Ayurveda) obtained through specialised heat treatment of pearls¹. The reported analysis of this 'bhasma' mentions the presence of only calcium and carbonate^{2,3}. In view of scanty information regarding the constituents of this product, it was considered worthwhile to analyse the pearl-bhasma by modern techniques.

Experimental

Excelar grade chemicals were used. Double-distilled deionised water was used for preparing solutions.

The atomic absorption spectra were recorded on a Varian AA-6 spectrometer, the ir spectra (KBr)